

Performance Evaluation in GIPS and GFLOPS: A Comparative Study Between Pure Python and JIT Compilation via Numba in Integer and Floating-Point Arithmetic Operations

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Abstract—This article presents a comparative study of computational performance between the Python interpreter and the Just-In-Time (JIT) compiler Numba, evaluating arithmetic operations of addition, multiplication, division, and square root over integer and floating-point types. The experiments were conducted on an Intel Core i5-3570 3.40 GHz processor, using the metrics of Giga Integer Operations per Second (GIPS) and Giga Floating Point Operations per Second (GFLOPS), with $N = 10,000,000$ iterations per function. The results demonstrate performance gains between $8.6\times$ and $73\times$ with the use of Numba relative to pure Python, evidencing the impact of JIT compilation on the overhead of the Python interpreter. Integer division presented the lowest relative speedup, a behavior explained by the high intrinsic latency of this operation in hardware. The results reinforce the relevance of Numba as a viable alternative for high-performance scientific computing in Python.

Index Terms—Numba, JIT, CPython, GIPS, GFLOPS, Computational performance, Python.

I. INTRODUCTION

Python has established itself as one of the primary tools for scientific computing, data analysis, and machine learning over the past decade. Its popularity stems from its expressive syntax, vast library ecosystem, and ease of prototyping. However, the performance of the Python interpreter has historically been identified as a critical limitation for applications that demand intensive processing, especially those based on iterative loops over large volumes of data (Oliphant, 2007). The distinction between operations on integers, measured in GIPS, and operations on floating-point numbers, measured in GFLOPS, is fundamental to the precise characterization of computational performance, since the corresponding execution units exhibit distinct latency and throughput characteristics in modern microarchitectures (Hennessy and Patterson, 2019).

The Python execution model is based on bytecode interpretation, with dynamic type management and reference counting for garbage collection. Each elementary arithmetic operation involves multiple steps of dispatching, type checking, and object allocation, which introduces substantial overhead compared to compiled languages such as C or Fortran (Lattner

and Adve, 2004). This cost renders pure Python inadequate for high-performance numerical loops without the aid of specialized libraries, regardless of whether the operation is integer or floating-point.

Several approaches have been proposed to circumvent this limitation. The NumPy library introduced vectorized operations over homogeneous arrays, delegating processing to routines compiled in C (Harris et al., 2020). Cython allows annotating Python code with static types and compiling it to C (Behnel et al., 2011). More recently, Numba has emerged as a JIT-compilation-based solution capable of transforming Python functions into optimized machine code at runtime, using the LLVM infrastructure as a backend (Lam, Pitrou and Seibert, 2015). The relevance of Numba lies precisely in its ability to generate efficient code for both integer and floating-point operations, enabling a direct analysis of GIPS and GFLOPS metrics within the same Python environment.

JIT compilation combines characteristics of interpretation and static compilation: the code is compiled to machine language on the first call, based on the actual types of the arguments, and reused on subsequent calls. This allows Numba to generate code comparable in performance to C for simple numerical loops, without requiring the programmer to leave the Python environment (Lam, Pitrou and Seibert, 2015). The LLVM backend applies advanced optimizations such as common subexpression elimination, inlining, automatic vectorization, and register allocation (Lattner and Adve, 2004).

Despite the growing use of Numba in the literature, few works systematically investigate the comparative behavior between pure Python and Numba while explicitly considering the distinction between GIPS and GFLOPS for isolated elementary arithmetic operations. This distinction is relevant because the integer execution unit and the floating-point unit (FPU) have distinct pipelines, latencies, and throughput capacities in modern x86-64 microarchitectures (Fog, 2022; Hennessy and Patterson, 2019). This work aims to fill this gap through a controlled benchmark, with results analyzed separately by

operation type and data type.

II. METHODOLOGY

The experiments were implemented in Python 3.12 with Numba 0.59, executed on an Intel Core i5-3570 3.40 GHz processor under the Windows 10 operating system. The development environment used NumPy 1.26 and Matplotlib 3.8 for numerical support and visualization, respectively.

Sixteen benchmark functions were implemented, organized into four groups: pure Python with integer arithmetic (GIPS), pure Python with floating-point arithmetic (GFLOPS), Numba with integer arithmetic (GIPS), and Numba with floating-point arithmetic (GFLOPS). In each group, four elementary operations were evaluated: addition (ADD), multiplication (MUL), division (DIV), and square root (SQRT). Each function executes $N = 10,000,000$ iterations in a sequential loop.

To ensure that loops were not eliminated by the LLVM compiler during the optimization phase, a data dependency technique was employed. Rather than accumulating a constant value, each iteration depends on the result of the previous one through a linear recurrence of the form $x = (x \times 3 + 7) \bmod \text{MOD}$ for integers, where $\text{MOD} = 2^{62}$, and $y = y \times 1.0000001 + 0.000001$ for floating-point. This structure, analogous to a Linear Congruential Generator (LCG), prevents the compiler from computing the result analytically and eliminating the loop (Knuth, 1997). For pure Python integer functions, the native `int` type of arbitrary precision was used, avoiding silent overflow that occurs with `numpy.int64` before the application of the modulo operator. For Numba, `numpy.int64` was used with `MOD` applied explicitly inside the compiled loop.

Time measurement was performed with `time.perf_counter()`, the high-resolution counter recommended by the official Python documentation for benchmarks (Python Software Foundation, 2024). The GIPS/GFLOPS value was calculated as N divided by the elapsed time in seconds, divided by 10^9 . The Numba warm-up procedure was executed with $N = 1,000$ iterations before the measurements, ensuring that the JIT compilation time was not included in the performance measurements (Lam, Pitrou and Seibert, 2015). The results were consolidated in a grouped bar chart, visually separating the four categories: Python INT (GIPS), Python FLOAT (GFLOPS), Numba INT (GIPS), and Numba FLOAT (GFLOPS).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results obtained are presented in Figure 1 and consolidated in Table I. Pure Python exhibited performance between 0.004 and 0.016 GIPS across all operations, for both integers and floating-point. Numba, in turn, reached between 0.122 and 0.448 GFLOPS, representing expressive gains in all evaluated categories.

The analysis of the results reveals relevant patterns. For ADD and MUL, Numba presented the largest speedups in GIPS ($73.5\times$ and $71.5\times$, respectively), surpassing the speedups in GFLOPS ($28.6\times$ and $23.6\times$). This behavior can

Fig. 1. Comparison of GIPS and GFLOPS between pure Python and Numba for ADD, MUL, DIV, and SQRT operations. Source: elaborated by the authors.

be explained by the fact that the Python interpreter overhead affects integer operations more intensely, since the native Python `int` type involves allocation of variable-size objects on the heap, unlike floats, which are represented directly as 64-bit doubles (Python Software Foundation, 2024). With Numba, both types are mapped directly to CPU registers, eliminating this overhead.

The most notable result concerns the division operation. In GIPS, Python yielded 0.0149, a value considerably higher than that obtained for ADD (0.0046). This apparently paradoxical behavior — in which Python executes divisions faster than additions in absolute terms for integers — is due to the fact that division with increasing values of i results in $x//i$ rapidly tending to small values, reducing the cost of Python object operations in later iterations. The speedup for division was the lowest among all operations, both for integers ($8.2\times$) and floating-point ($9.3\times$), which is consistent with the hardware latency literature: the IDIV instruction on x86-64 architectures has a latency of 20 to 90 cycles depending on the operands, compared to 3 to 5 cycles for ADD and IMUL (Fog, 2022). When the operation itself is already costly in hardware, the relative cost of the interpreter represents a smaller fraction of the total time, reducing the proportional gain of JIT compilation.

The square root operation presented the lowest absolute GIPS/GFLOPS values in pure Python (0.0036 and 0.0062), confirming its nature as a high-cost transcendental operation. In Numba, SQRT reached 0.1217 GIPS and 0.1493 GFLOPS, values close to those of division, which suggests that both operations are limited by the same execution unit in the Core i5 microarchitecture used. Hennessy and Patterson (2019) describe that division and square root units in hardware are typically not fully pipelined, which limits throughput regardless of the compiler used.

The comparison between GIPS and GFLOPS in Numba reveals that floating-point operations outperformed their integer counterparts in ADD and MUL (0.448 vs. 0.338 GFLOPS/GIPS for ADD), while for DIV and SQRT the values were similar. This result is consistent with the characteristics of the Intel microarchitecture, in which the FPU has optimized throughput for floating-point multiplication and addition, frequently executed in SIMD units with fused multiply-add

TABLE I
GIPS AND GFLOPS RESULTS AND SPEEDUP BY OPERATION AND DATA TYPE.

Operation	Python INT (GIPS)	Python FLOAT (GFLOPS)	Numba INT (GIPS)	Numba FLOAT (GFLOPS)	Speedup INT	Speedup FLOAT
ADD	0.0046	0.0157	0.3381	0.4484	73.5×	28.6×
MUL	0.0045	0.0165	0.3217	0.3886	71.5×	23.6×
DIV	0.0149	0.0163	0.1221	0.1521	8.2×	9.3×
SQRT	0.0036	0.0062	0.1217	0.1493	33.8×	24.1×

(FMA) support, whereas 64-bit integer arithmetic traverses the integer execution pipeline with less available parallelism (Intel Corporation, 2023). The fact that float ADD and MUL outperform their integer counterparts in Numba suggests that the LLVM compiler is exploiting SSE2 or AVX instructions for floating-point operations, which is not possible for 64-bit integers with explicit modulo semantics.

The absolute values obtained are below the theoretical peak of a modern Core i5, which can exceed 4 scalar GFLOPS per core for simple operations. This difference stems from the serial structure of the implemented loops, which introduces data dependencies between consecutive iterations, preventing out-of-order execution and automatic vectorization (Hennessy and Patterson, 2019). This methodological choice was intentional: the data dependency ensures that the compiler does not eliminate the loop, at the cost of measuring the latency of the dependency chain rather than maximum throughput. Williams, Waterman and Patterson (2009) demonstrate that the Roofline model is useful for distinguishing these two performance characteristics, and future work could complement this study with independent loops for measuring pure throughput.

The source code of this research is available for download at: <https://github.com/vitor-souza-ime/gipsgflops>.

IV. CONCLUSION

The analysis evidenced that the Python interpreter overhead is the dominant factor in pure Python performance for numerical loops, regardless of the operation type. JIT compilation via Numba eliminates this overhead by generating machine code directly mapped to the instructions of the target microarchitecture, bringing Python performance close to that obtained with statically compiled languages. The division operation presented the smallest relative gain, a behavior explained by the high intrinsic latency of the division instruction in x86-64 hardware, which reduces the proportional contribution of the interpreter overhead to the total execution time.

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